

Synthesis of Some Substituted Pyrazoles as Possible Antibacterial Agents

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Manuscript received 26 November 1976, revised 28 July 1977, accepted 29 July 1977.

Some pyrazole derivatives of the type II-VI were synthesised from 4-(3', 5'-Dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) benzhydrazide (I) and tested against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Only type III-compounds completely inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* at the concentrations employed.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDES have been reported to possess antitubercular¹ and antifungal² activity. Triazole nucleus itself has been associated with diverse biological activities³, while some oxadiazoles show pesticidal properties⁴. Hence it was thought of interest to prepare some thiosemicarbazides, triazoles, oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles in order to study their antibacterial activities.

3,5-Dimethyl-1-(*p*-carboxyphenyl)-1(H) pyrazole⁵ on esterification followed by treatment with hydrazine hydrate yielded the hydrazide (I) which on condensation with aromatic aldehydes, gave the corresponding N-benzylidene derivatives (II). Thiosemicarbazides (III) were obtained by condensing aryl isothiocyanates⁶ with I. III on cyclization with aqueous alkali^{7,8} gave the desired triazoles (IV) while with Iodine and alkali, the oxadiazoles (V) were obtained. Thiadiazoles (VI) were prepared by cyclizing III with concentrated sulphuric acid⁹.

Compound V (Ar = phenyl) was also synthesised alternatively, by condensing I with Phenylisocyanate followed by cyclization with Phosphorus oxychloride. IR-spectra of the two products were superimposable and mixture—m.p. did not show any depression.

Experimental

All the mps. are recorded by open-capillary method and are uncorrected.

4-(3',5'-Dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) benzhydrazide (I) :

3,5-Dimethyl-1-(*p*-carboxyphenyl)-1(H) pyrazole (15 g) was dissolved in ethanol (60 ml), saturated with HCl gas and refluxed for 12 hr. The mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-cold water (400 ml) and basified with NaHCO₃. The product was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in vacuum. The crude ester (m.p. 60-62°) was used as such without purification.

The ethyl ester (0.05 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (95%, 0.1 mole) were refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) for 12 hr, concentrated under reduced

pressure and the solid obtained on cooling was filtered. It was crystallized from aq. methanol (10%), m.p. 88°, yield (9.2 g, 80%), [Found : C 62.54, H 6.33, N 24.08 ; C₁₂H₁₄N₄O requires C 62.61, H 6.09, N 24.35%]

4-(3', 5'-Dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) phenyl-N-benzilidinohydrazides (II.....Table 1) :

Equimolar quantities of hydrazide (I) and an appropriate aromatic aldehyde were refluxed in ethanol for 2 hr. Addition of a few drops of acetic acid improved the yields. Product separated on cooling were filtered, washed with ether and crystallized from ethanol (yields 65-80%).

1-[*p*-(3',5'-Dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) benzoyl]-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides (III.....Table 2) :

To a solution of I (0.01 mole) in ethanol (10 ml), was added with stirring an appropriate aromatic isothiocyanate (0.011 mole) in the same solvent (10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. The solid product obtained on cooling was filtered, washed with ether and crystallized from ethanol (yields 75-85%).

4-Aryl-3-mercapto-5-[*p*-(3',5'-dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) phenyl]-1,2,4-triazoles (IV.....Table 3) :

The thiosemicarbazide III (0.01 mole) and NaOH (2N, 40 ml) were refluxed for 2 hr. The solution was filtered, cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The solid product thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallized aq. ethanol (yields 65-75%).

2-Arylamino-5-[*p*-(3',5'-dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) phenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (V.....Table 4) :

Compound III (0.01 mole) was dissolved in a cold solution of NaOH (4 N, 5 ml). Iodine in KI (5%) was then added dropwise with stirring and cooling till the colour of Iodine persisted. The mixture was refluxed and more Iodine solution was added till a permanent tinge of Iodine remained. It was then cooled and poured in ice-cold water. The

precipitated solid was filtered, washed with a dil. $Na_2S_2O_3$ and then with water. The compound was crystallized from a 1 : 1 mixture of DMF-ethanol (yields 55-65%).

Alternatively, V (Ar = phenyl) was prepared by refluxing I (0.005 mole) and phenylisocyanate (0.006 mole) in alcohol (20 ml) for 6 hr. The product (VII) separated on cooling, was filtered, washed with cold methanol and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 123° , yield (1.57 g, 90%).

The semicarbazide (VII) was heated with $POCl_3$ (10 ml) at $80^\circ C$ for 4 hr. The liquid was cooled and poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained

was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from a 1 : 1 mixture of DMF-ethanol, m.p. 240° , yield (1.02 g, 62%).

2-Arylamino,-5-[p-(3',5'-dimethyl-1'-pyrazolyl) phenyl]-1,2,4-thiadiazole (VI. ... Table 5) :

The thiosemicarbazide II (0.01 mole) was added in small portions to conc. H_2SO_4 (100 ml) at 0° . The mixture was stirred at 0° for 3 hr. more. It was allowed to stand overnight at room-temperature and then poured over crushed ice. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with oil. NH_4OH followed by water and crystallized from aq. methanol (yields 35-50%).

TABLE 1—4-(3', 5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PYRAZOLYL) PHENYL-N-BENZYLIDINOHYDRAZIDE (II)

Sl. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis	
				Calcd. %N	Found
1.	C ₆ H ₅	233	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	17.55	17.67
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	197	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	16.75	16.56
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	159	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	16.73	16.62
4.	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	176	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	16.05	15.93
5.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	208	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	19.12	18.97
6.	2-Furyl	118	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	18.18	18.10

TABLE 2—1-[p-(3', 5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PYRAZOLYL) BENZOYL]-4-ARYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDES (III)

Sl. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis	
				Calcd. %S	Found
7.	C ₆ H ₅	118	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	8.77	8.38
8.	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	178	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	8.44	8.21
9.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	190	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ OSCl	8.03	8.11

TABLE 3—4-ARYL-3-MERCAPTO-5-[p-(3', 5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PYRAZOLYL) PHENYL]-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLES (IV)

Sl. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis	
				Calcd. %S	Found
10.	C ₆ H ₅	271	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	9.22	9.38
11.	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	245	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	8.91	8.79
12.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	263	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ SCl	8.39	8.51

TABLE 4—2-ARYLAMINO-5-[p-(3', 5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PYRAZOLYL) PHENYL]-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLES (V)

Sl. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis	
				Calcd. %N	Found
13.	C ₆ H ₅	238	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	21.18	21.03
14.	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	240	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	20.41	20.11
15.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	260	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ OCl	19.15	19.32

TABLE 5—2-ARYLAMINO-5-[p-(3', 5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PYRAZOLYL) PHENYL]-1, 3, 4-THIADIAZOLES (VI)

Sl. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis	
				Calcd. %C	Found
16.	C ₆ H ₅	199	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	9.22	9.31
17.	4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	195	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	8.91	9.03
18.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	225	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ SCl	8.39	8.62

Screening for antibacterial activity

All the compounds from No. 1 to 18 were screened *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* using concentration levels of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 mg/ml. Compound nos. 7-9 completely inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* at all concentrations employed while compound nos. 1-6 were only effective at the level of 2 mg/ml. Except compound nos. 7-9 which slightly inhibited the growth at 2 mg/ml. none others were effective against *E. coli*.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to UNICHEM Laboratories, Bombay, for microbiological testing of the compounds and also to Rev. Fr. L. Pereira, S.J., Principal, St. Xavier's College for providing the laboratory facilities.

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